

DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF USING EDUCATIONAL TASKS IN THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING THE NATIVE LANGUAGE IN PRIMARY GRADES

Kuranbayeva Khusnora Abdullayevna

Lecturer, Department of Pedagogy, Tashkent
State Pedagogical University (TAFU)
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences,
Acting Associate Professor
E-mail: husnorakuranbaeva@gmail.com
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Annotation. The current state and prospects for the transition to a credit-modular system in the development of independent learning assignments for students majoring in philology, the principles of the credit-modular system based on the best international practices of higher education institutions, recognition of students' learning outcomes, the creation of opportunities for independent formation of an educational trajectory and the introduction of academic mobility, the accumulation of grades, the interest of the professor and students in the subject, and a clearly defined grading system are substantiated.

Keywords: Credit module, educational trajectory, academic mobility, liberalization of education, academic credits, quantitative equivalents, credit units, educational object, conveyor, individualization, module, structural-thematic, organizational-structural principle, block of disciplines, relative thematic isolation, credit technology of education, principle of systematicity and consistency, principle of activity, principle of individual approach, principle of accessibility, presentability, project, credit-modular system ECTS.

Introduction

Within the process of liberalizing education and upbringing that began in the 18th century, academic credits were introduced for the first time in the 19th century in U.S. universities. The establishment of quantitative equivalents through credits allowed students to master educational programs according to the content and division of learning units, enabling them to independently plan their educational process. Profound reforms in quality control and evaluation systems created the conditions and technologies for improving the educational process.

The credit-modular system, as a means of academic mobility and learning activity, reflects the European educational model which emphasizes high student engagement. The educational process not only involves learning as an object but also allows individuals themselves to directly influence the system. On the one

hand, this requires a high degree of student self-awareness, and on the other, it demands a transformation in the relationship between students and teachers.

Unlike traditional education, where a student follows a predetermined uniform curriculum or “conveyor,” the credit-modular system allows for the inclusion of various modules beyond the compulsory subjects, thus enabling the creation of an individual learning plan. Therefore, in the modular-credit system, independent learning methods—directed by the personal needs of the student—serve as a guarantee of quality education. During the learning process, each student earns credits that serve as a measure of the labor intensity of the student’s academic work.

This system also supports a project-based form of teaching aimed at developing and protecting the individual, including the implementation of group projects on specific topics. Other advantages of this system include the simultaneous study of fewer subjects, the individualization of the pedagogical process, its practical orientation, and the revelation of students’ creative abilities. Under modern conditions, this system enables the training of more mobile, competent, and in-demand specialists.

Problem Statement

Filling the concept of “module” with real content has become an urgent issue for all universities today. Practice shows that determining the basis for forming modules is difficult. There may be several approaches: assembling modules according to a structural-thematic or an organizational-structural principle. The concept of a module can be understood in two ways. In the first case, a module is considered as a block of subjects that form a coherent whole within an educational program, viewed as a logical substructure within the overall structure of the program.

The degree of independence of an educational module is determined by its relative thematic isolation. Here, a module is interpreted as a unit of the educational program that represents a set of subjects corresponding to the qualification requirements of the field of study.

A large amount of learning material is produced for independent research and development. Within the framework of independent activities, additional training sessions are conducted under the supervision of teachers, while deans prepare special schedules and timetables.

An analysis of scientific studies and publications shows that scholars such as Y. Babansky, A. Verbitsky, L. Derkach, V. Kazakov, O. Kirichuk, B. Korotyayev, A. Kucheryavy, S. Matushkin, A. Moroz, N. Nikandrov, P. Pidkasisty, and N.

Polovnikova have studied various aspects of organizing students' independent work. Similarly, V. Slastenin, T. Shamova, V. Aksenova, T. Gusak, V. Krylov, V. Leontiev, G. Shchukina, and V. Vergasov have examined issues related to motivating students' learning activities.

The ways of improving students' preparation for independent academic work have been analyzed by M. Antonyuk, V. Buryak, N. Vazheyevskaya, L. Derkach, I. Mostovaya, L. Onuchak, M. Soldatenko, and others. The modular system of organizing education has been thoroughly studied by A. Aleksyuk, K. Vazina, A. Kucheryavy, A. Gumenyuk, B. Ognevyuk, A. Furman, and P. Yusevichene.

Issues related to self-education and self-development have been developed by N. Bityanova, A. Gromseva, S. Dneprov, V. Kurinsky, and L. Ruvinsky. Various aspects of the scientific organization of learning activities have been addressed by S. Arkhangelsky, Ya. Ludchenko, and others. Despite the attention of many scholars and practitioners to the problem of organizing university students' independent work, significant issues that require reflection and resolution still remain.

Ensuring the effectiveness of the credit technology system and maintaining the quality of education require careful consideration of its technological and methodological components: credit technologies, standards, curricula, job descriptions, principles for selecting course content, teaching methods, organization of the educational process, and the system of students' independent work (SIW) within the credit framework.

Solution Method

In official sources, the concept of "credit" is defined as a unified measure of the volume of academic work performed by a student and a teacher. One credit corresponds to one academic hour per week of classroom work during an academic term. Each academic hour of a lecture, practical (seminar), or studio session must be complemented by a student's independent work—two hours (100 minutes) for undergraduate students and four hours (200 minutes) for graduate students.

The technology of credit-based education is a method of organizing the educational process in which students can individually plan the sequence of their learning trajectory. The essence of the credit technology lies in the fact that the labor intensity of academic work is measured in credits, which describe the volume of learned material. One of the main tasks of the credit-based education system is to increase the role of students' independent work.

Consultations on the most difficult issues of the curriculum, homework, reports, and other types of IWS assignments are included in the students' independent work (IWS) hours. The content of the student's independent work is necessarily reflected in the subject's syllabus and academic program. Students' independent work represents an active and purposeful way of mastering new knowledge and skills by the student without the direct participation of the teacher.

The development of students' ability for independent learning, their creative activity and initiative, as well as the organizational measures that ensure the proper functioning of students' independent work in general, must be based on the following conditions:

- independent study must correspond to the thematic direction of the discipline;
- independent learning must be carried out effectively, accompanied by continuous monitoring and evaluation of its results.

To organize students' independent work effectively, a higher education teacher must know and adhere to the following organizational principles: the principle of systematization and consistency; the principle of activity; the principle of individual approach; the principle of accessibility; and the principle of scientifically based time management and homework performance. The topics and content of students' independent work are determined by state educational standards, current curricula, model and working syllabi of subjects, basic literature such as textbooks, teaching manuals and methodological guides, as well as additional literature.

The control and evaluation of independent work are organized as a unity of two forms:

- self-control and self-assessment by the student;
- monitoring and assessment by teachers, state examination and attestation commissions, and other relevant bodies.

Independent learning in pedagogical higher education is a specific means of organizing and managing students' independent activity in the educational process, serving as a means of self-organization and self-education in mastering professional skills. An analysis of the existing scientific, psychological, and pedagogical literature demonstrates various approaches and an ambiguous definition of the concept of "students' independent work." IWS is regarded as a form of educational and scientific cognition, a form of organizing learning, a teaching method, a means of creative thinking, and a tool of instruction.

Measures that create the necessary conditions and environment for performing independent work include the following resources for each student:

- informational resources (reference books, class materials, task banks, curricula, software packages, etc.);

- methodological materials (guidelines, manuals, workshops, workbooks, etc.);

- control materials (tests, case studies);

- material resources (laboratories, measuring instruments, etc.);

- time resources;

- consultations;

- the possibility of choosing an individual learning trajectory (through elective courses);

- the opportunity for public discussion of theoretical and/or practical results independently obtained by the student (in conferences, Olympiads, and competitions).

Forms of IWS

The *summary* is a 4–12-page A10 format paper in Times New Roman font, 14 pt, presenting or critically reviewing a topic. Its structure is traditional: title page, introduction, main part, conclusions, and list of references. The abstract may be presented for group discussion. The *report* is a brief summary of the main principles of a topic, lasting 3–5 minutes. The *synopsis* is a concise description of a topic in a standard 2–4-page workbook format, highlighting key concepts. The *glossary* is a list of concepts and terms on a given topic arranged in a table. The *case* is a situation requiring a solution during group analysis; the group consists of 3–4 people who independently discuss the problem and develop solutions. The results are presented to the group in the form of a final report presentation.

The *report* provides a written and oral description of the results obtained during study, key problems, and proposed solutions. The *presentation* is a form of delivering information, with or without technical means, often used to introduce new ideas, projects, or services. It typically includes text and illustrations in a unified graphic style. The *project* involves individual or group research on a topic that includes searching for, collecting, and analyzing necessary information. The *debate* is a discussion of previously prepared issues with conclusions.

From a didactic perspective, independent learning serves as one of the main methods of acquiring knowledge, skills, and competencies, as well as one of the organizational forms of education. The educational role of independent work lies

in the fact that it is an active means of developing the personal qualities of future specialists.

E. L. Belkin defines the pedagogical foundations of students' independent work, while V. A. Belovolov and S. P. Belovolova consider the issues of organizing and structuring students' independent activities. The term "independent work" is used differently by various authors depending on how they interpret the concept of "independence": the student performs the task independently without the teacher's direct participation; the student thinks independently and directs themselves toward the learning material; and many researchers define "independent work" as activities carried out outside the classroom, as opposed to compulsory (in-class) learning.

It has become traditional to define students' independent work as a part of the educational process that the student conducts without the direct participation of the teacher, planning and performing it autonomously. K. K. Gomoyunov also refers to independent learning as planned work performed by students under the teacher's methodological guidance but without their direct involvement. This definition, in our opinion, accurately reflects the content of extracurricular independent student work (IWS) under the credit system of education.

The credit-based education system provides for two types of students' independent work:

- extracurricular independent work (IWS), planned by the teacher but carried out without their direct participation;
- classroom independent work (IWS), performed by the student under the teacher's guidance but also planned in advance.

It is beyond doubt that the development of students' independent activity serves as a prerequisite for their transition toward self-education.

Results and Examples

Under the conditions of the credit-based education system, each student is provided with a complete set of organizational and methodological materials, including the curriculum and lecture notes. Therefore, classroom sessions with the teacher have a consultative character, and lectures are shortened to allow students to discuss materials studied independently beforehand and to prepare for scientific dialogue. Independent, active, and purposeful learning of educational materials by students, organized by the teacher through the formation and activation of self-management techniques and methods, serves as the main and leading form of students' educational activity. Thus, there is no

doubt that organizing students' independent work plays a priority role in the credit-based education system.

The extensive use of recommended methods for independent learning stimulates intellectual and practical activities, develops the student's intellectual abilities, and ensures their continuous pursuit of knowledge in the future.

In the pedagogical higher education system, the methodology of teaching the native language in primary schools involves examining the current state of the use of educational assignments, types of tasks, functional differentiation of questions and assignments, and the role of exercises in the methodology of teaching native and state languages. Attention is also paid to the correspondence of the prepared educational tasks to the chosen topic and educational objectives, as well as the development of future specialists' skills in creating assignments. The existing state of using educational tasks in the methodology of teaching the native language based on the credit-module system, particularly in higher education institutions during Uzbek language teaching methodology classes, has been analytically studied. The content of questions, exercises, and assignments in textbooks designed for the training of future teachers of native language and literature has been examined. In addition, research aimed at improving educational assignments from pedagogical and pragmatic perspectives has been analyzed.

The current state of using educational tasks in the methodology of teaching the native language in primary schools—specifically, in Uzbek language teaching methodology classes in higher education institutions—was studied analytically. Research conducted in recent years to improve educational assignments was also partially reviewed. The study examined the current state and prospects of transitioning to a credit-module system in the development of speech competence among future primary school teachers in pedagogical higher education. It justified the appropriateness of introducing the principles of the credit-module system in higher education institutions based on advanced international experiences, creating opportunities for learners to independently design their learning trajectories, ensuring academic mobility, the accumulation of grades, and fostering interest in subjects among professors and students.

An integrative-methodological approach to improving students' independent learning activities at higher education institutions based on the credit-module system and the operation of Academic Resource Centers (ARC) was analyzed. The activities of higher education institutions, local self-governing bodies, and independently managed educational institutions were also examined.

The creation of new-generation textbooks for pedagogical higher education institutions based on advanced international experiences is grounded in the principles of the credit-module system. It is important to note that organizing learner-centered education, achieving transparency, enhancing flexibility, and strengthening student mobility are key components of the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS), which consists of two essential elements.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the current state of using educational assignments in the methodology of teaching the native language in primary schools, as well as the inclusion of questions, exercises, and assignments in Uzbek language teaching methodology classes, has been analytically studied. Research conducted to improve educational assignments from didactic and theoretical perspectives has also been analyzed. The higher education system is transitioning to a credit-module system to teach students independent learning and evaluate their academic performance.

Under such conditions, students mainly complete the assignments independently, which are uploaded to platforms by teachers and presented to learners. The most effective way to teach students independent learning in higher education is to design educational tasks aimed at encouraging students to engage in self-directed research. The obtained results show that the criterion for evaluating learning efficiency is greater than one, and the criterion for assessing the level of cognition is greater than zero. This indicates that the academic achievement of the experimental group is higher than that of the control group. Hence, the experimental work conducted to determine the development level of students' independent learning and speech skills proved to be effective. Any form of education and teaching methodology must be developed with an evaluation criterion. For students specializing in primary education at pedagogical higher education institutions, it is advisable to develop independent learning assignments and assessment criteria based on both international and local experiences. Our recommendations are also based on this approach. Independent learning assignments in philological education in primary schools are particularly essential for today's credit-module education system.

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